
**THE INTERPRETATION OF THE IMAGE OF WOLVES IN CHINGIZ
AITMATOV'S KIYAMAT**

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Abstract: This article describes the tragic end of the fate of Akbara and Toshchainar, a pair of wolves and their offspring. The struggle of good and evil in the life of wolves, the relationship between man and nature is analyzed.

Key words: Akbara, Toshchainar, Mo'yinqum, exile, descent, doomsday, goodness, evil, wolf, Boston.

Chingiz Torakulovich Aitmatov is one of the most talented and world-famous figures of Kyrgyz literature of the 20th century. He was born on December 12, 1928 in Shakar Ovul, Talas Valley, Kyrgyzstan. In the novel "Doomsday" (1986), universal aspects of our time, strong philosophical, moral and social problems were raised.

The main characters in "Qiyamat" are wolves Akbara and Toshchainar, who unite the whole novel into one plot system. In the events, only a pair of wolves - Akbara and Toshchainar act as a chain, and all the events depend on these wolves. Events are based on the bitter fate of wolves. The novel mainly focuses on Akbara's mental state and character.

The shepherds of this area named him Toshchainar because his teeth were sharp as daggers and he was ready to throw anything at the wolf. At first, the shepherds called the she-wolf Aqdil, who was completely amazed by her crystal-clear eyes when she saw someone close by. After some time, they called him Akbara - Great. Akbara, the wolf who felt all the unconscious feelings of motherhood and felt the first happy moments of motherhood, gave up her children several times in the trials of fate. In the persecution, the terrible situation reached such a level that it seemed as if the end of the world was coming, and the earth and the sky were turning upside down. Akbara and Toshchainar will live here for another year, and their next attempt to breed will be unsuccessful. A year later, the apocalypse broke out in the reed fields of Aldashboyi. A reed field is set on fire to make way for a mountain mine. The ashes of five wolf cubs are buried in the blue together with the reeds. Now Akbara and Toshchainar will go far away from these places, to the mountains where it is difficult for a human foot to reach. This was their last chance to reproduce.

Akbara and Toshchainar started life again...

They built a child. This time there were four of them. It was a last-ditch effort to procreate. The story of the wolves in Issyk-Kol ended with an unprecedented tragedy.

While Bozorboy Noygutov was delivering a group of geologists back to the destination, he suddenly encountered four wolf cubs and stole them from their den in an attempt to earn money.

Every time wolves lose their children, humans are the main culprit. Land appropriation by humans, destruction of forests, violation of the ancient rules of nature, and ultimately the displacement of creatures from their native homes are depicted at the apocalyptic level. They attack saigas in order to get meat products, they are brutally slaughtered. In such turmoil, wolf cubs also become victims. Alcoholic shepherd Bozorboy takes the wolves from their nest and runs away in order to sell them for good money. As a result of such heinous acts of man, Boston accidentally shoots his little child, kills Bozorboy, and dies himself. Human relationships are so diverse, their nature and character are so diverse and complex that even the most perfect, most modern computer systems cannot distinguish the general outline of the simplest human nature. The story of Akbara and Toshchainar, the main characters in the work, the fate of wandering and the fact that humanity is the cause of the tragedy is vividly reflected in the work. In the novel "Doomsday", the situation of goodness and humanity, goodness and correctness, justice and righteousness, falling to the level of Doomsday is revealed by reflecting the problems of nature, society, man and faith. The work reveals the struggle between good and evil since the beginning of mankind, the relationship between man and nature through wolves and their lives. We can say that the work consists of separate stories, and among them there is an independent event. In Aitmatov's works, the eternal struggle, that is, the struggle between good and evil, is promoted, and in most cases evil wins. It is the same in this work. Wolves lose their children several times. Avdey dies. Jesus Christ hangs on the cross. Boston will be the murderer of his child. The strong psychological impact of the play is that evil always wins. The idea does not come by itself. There are such strange people in life, and the fact that these people were written and retreated from the utopia we are used to has contributed to the greatness of the work.

Aitmatov is a skillful writer who is able to describe the essence of goodness in a variety of ways: in close connection with theological, philosophical, and humane foundations, and at the same time, he has deep knowledge and logic.

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